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Improvisation And Utilization Of Instructional Materials For Effective Teaching And Learning Agricultural Science Education In Secondary Schools In Yobe South Senatorial Zone, Yobe , Nigeria State

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ABSTRACT

A structured survey was administered to collect data on improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning agricultural science education in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone, Yobe state. The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to identify significant improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning Agricultural science education in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone, Yobe state, Nigeria. The outcome of the research reveal that Based on the findings of the research question regarding the improvisation of instructional materials for teaching and learning Agricultural science in senior secondary school in Yobe south senatorial zone. Item 1 shows a mean of 2.05 therefore there is no provision of teaching facilities for effective teaching of Agricultural science. Item 2 shows the mean of 2.05 which implies that many Agricultural science teachers do not improvised instructional materials in their teaching activities. Item 3 shows the mean of 2.40 and this implies that there is no fund meant for the production of instructional materials for teaching and learning

Keywords: Improvisation, utilization, instructional materials

INTRODUCTION

There are many literatures on the utilization of instructional materials, the relevant materials utilized by a teachers during Agricultural Science instructional process are to facilitate teaching and learning for the purpose of making the content of the instruction more practical and less vague. Improvisation means to make without extensive preparation and using those materials and devices that are locally available within the environment and do not involve high cost. In providing alternative or substitute to factory made imported equipment (Obianwu, 1996). According to Ugwueke as cited in Owuamamana (2007) Improvisation refers to selection or provision of substitute for something not readily available. It is a process by which educational materials can be designed and developed using local available materials to meet specific instructional needs. Improvisation is linked with the concept of self-reliance. When the available resources in our environment are used, they help as spend less on importing an expensive commercially produced media. In the course of improvisation models are always similar in appearance to

the thing they respect. However they may be of the same size, smaller or bigger than the things they respect (Owuamaman, 2017). Some local materials that can be used for improvisation include the following: bamboos for making of test tubes and pipetters, discarded wood or metal sheets for fabricated mould or mockups, bottle tops, local plants, seeds and rocks are all primary resources to a creative teacher. (Obianwu, 1996). Improvisation can be bringing out inherent talent in pupils and teachers in the long run will lead to our self-sufficient in both human and materials resources.

Improvised instructional materials are teaching materials designed and produced from the available local materials in order to promote effective teaching and learning in schools. They are materials that are used in the absence of the original or the ideal objects to bring about the some learning effect that the standard materials would have brought (Ahmed, 2008). Ndianrangu, Kathurl and Mungul (2003) investigate the effective used of improvised materials designed by science teachers during the teaching practice. This study presented evidence that improvised teaching aid designed by science teachers during practice had a great influence in the teaching of science in schools. These materials were found to be durable and could last for a longer time to enhance effective teaching and learning of science in schools that are unable to afford expensive standardized instructional materials, science teachers should be encourage to make their own teaching resource from the locally available materials to teach science.

Statement of the Problem

Many Agricultural Science teachers in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone do not make good improvisation and utilization of instructional materials. Even if there is enough practical apparatus in the schools laboratory, they fail to use them efficiently, instead they sticks to the traditional method of delivering lessons to students, forgetting that the teaching of Agricultural sciences education requires experiments and manipulation of apparatus by the students.

This research work will look at the problem of improvisation and utilization of apparatus and other instructional materials by the teachers towards teachers Agricultural Science in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone, Yobe State. Hence the instructional are basically used with the potential to capture and sustain learners' attention and also provide skills and improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning process. The effectiveness of its improvisation and utilization depends on the skills of the users (teachers). If this is the case then it's very important to know how experience and skillful our secondary schools teachers are and to what extent they use this experience of manipulating apparatus and other materials during teaching and learning process. Therefore, with this the research study will investigate the standard improvisation of instructional materials in teaching Agricultural Science in secondary schools Yobe south senatorial zone.

Objective of the study

1. To fine out the application of instructional materials among Agricultural science teachers in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone of Nigeria
2. To determine the level of local materials available for improvisation.
3. to find out the roles of improvisation toward enhancing teaching and learning of Agricultural Science
4. To examine the teachers application of instructional materials in teaching of Agricultural science in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone.

Research Questions

1. How often are the instructional materials applied in teaching of Agricultural science in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone?
2. To what extent are the instructional materials improvised by Agricultural science teachers in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?
3. What are the roles of improvisation of instructional materials in effective teaching Agricultural Science in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?
4. What are the challenges faced by Agricultural Science teachers in improvisation of instructional
5. materials in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research Design

A structured survey research design was administered and data was collected on improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning agricultural science education in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone, Yobe state. The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to identify significant improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning agricultural science education in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone, Yobe state

Area of the Study

The study was conducted among Agricultural Science teachers in secondary schools within Yobe south senatorial zone which comprises of Schools in Potiskum, Fika, Nanagere and Funi local government areas of Yobe state. The total population of the zone is approximately 483,346 as reported by the National Bureau of Statistics (2022) and 2,855 teachers, Nigerian Research and Development Council (NERDC). The study focused on twenty (20) Agricultural science teacher's in each local government, making a total of eighty (80) respondents within the zone.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of Agricultural science in all government secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone which encompasses of Fika, Potiskum, Nangere and Fune local Government areas of Yobe State. The schools are as follows as indicated in table 1 below.

Table 1: Yobe south senatorial zone local Government areas

Local Government	Schools
Fika L.G.A	- GSS Fika - GDSS Fika
Fune L.G.A	- GGSTC Damagum - GDSS Damagum
Nangere L.G.A	- GSS Nangere - GDSS Nangere
Potiskum L.G.A	- Fika Government - GDSS Potiskum

Sample and Sample Techniques

Twenty (20) Agricultural Science teachers were selected randomly from two (2) selected schools from each local government as shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Population of the Respondents

Local Government	Schools	Respondents
Fika L.G.A	- GSS Fika - GDSS Fika	10 10
Fune L.G.A	- GGSTC Damagum - GDSS Damagum	10 10
Nangere L.G.A	- GSS Nangere - GDSS Nangere	10 10
Potiskum L.G.A	- Fika Government - GDSS Potiskum	10 10
Total		80

Instruments for Data Collection

The researcher used questionnaire as instrument for data collect which was made up of questions arranged systematically based on the research questions and information were collected from Agricultural science

teacher in the schools within the zone. Four point scales was used to analyzed the results obtained as strongly agree (SA) = 4point, Agreed (A) = 3points, Disagreed (D) = 2points and strongly disagreed (SD) = 1point

Validation of Instrument

The instrument, questionnaire was validated by three lecturers in the school of secondary education (Vocational), Department of Agricultural science education for both face and content validation. Ugo (2020) suggested that instrument should be given to expert to review the items and also make a comment, this is to ensure not only the face validity of the instrument but also its content validity.

Method of Data of Collection

The main instrument for the collection of data was structured questionnaire. The instrument for data collection developed has two sections, A and B. section A deals with the bio-data of the respondents while section B deals with information on Improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning Agricultural Science Education in Secondary Schools in Yobe South Senatorial Zone, Yobe State, Nigeria was used and data were collected.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A descriptive statistic was involve using the likart scale.

Decision rule: a cut of point of 2.50 was used to determine the mean which was obtained as follows

$$\text{Thus } \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

This mean that any mean score equal to or greater than 2.50 was considered as accepted and any mean score less than 2.50 was considered as rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *How often are the instructional materials applied in teaching of Agricultural science in secondary schools in Yobe south senatorial zone?*

Table 3: Total means of the respondents on the problem in using instructional materials.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	NR	Mean	Remarks
1	There is provision of teaching facilities for effective teaching of Agricultural science	2 (4)	2 (3)	11 (2)	5 (1)	20	2.05	Rejected
2	Agricultural science teachers improvised instructional materials in teaching and learning	4 (4)	0 (3)	9 (2)	7 (1)	20	2.05	Rejected
3	There is fund meant for the production of instructional materials for teaching and learning agriculture	3 (4)	2 (3)	12 (2)	8 (1)	20	2.40	Rejected
4	Agricultural science Teachers produce instructional materials for teaching and learning	3 (4)	2 (3)	9 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.10	Rejected
5	Agricultural science teachers use improvised facilities in teaching Agriculture	2 (4)	2 (3)	10 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.00	Rejected
6	The school management encourages teachers to improvised instructional materials	6 (4)	5 (3)	5 (2)	4 (1)	20	2.65	Accepted
7	Agricultural science teachers are motivated to adopt the use of modern technologies to produce facilities for teaching Agric.	8 (4)	7 (3)	4 (2)	1 (1)	20	3.10	Accepted

Keys: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, NR = Number of Respondents.

In the table 3 above, item 1 shows a mean of 2.05 therefore there is no provision of teaching facilities for effective teaching of Agricultural science. Item 2 shows the mean of 2.05 which implies that many Agricultural science teachers do not improvised instructional materials in their teaching activities. Item 3 shows the mean of 2.40 and this implies that there is no fund meant for the production of instructional materials for teaching and learning. Item 4 also have the mean of 2.10 which shows that Agricultural science teachers do not produced instructional materials for their teaching activities. Item 5 in the other hand shows the mean of 2.00 therefore it is also rejected point. Item 6 shows that school management encourage teachers to improvised instructional materials with 2.65 mean point. Lastly item 7 have 3.10 mean which shows that Agricultural science teachers are motivated to adopt the use of modern technologies to produce facilities for their teaching activities.

Research Question Two: *To what extent are the instructional materials improvised by Agricultural science teachers in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?*

Table 4. Means of the respondents on the attitude of teachers toward improvisation of instructional materials for teaching and learning Agricultural science.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	NR	Mean	Remarks
8	Improvisation is beneficial to the academic achievement of students	14 (4)	6 (3)	0 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.70	Accepted
9	Knowledge of improvisation enables teacher to be self-fulfilled teacher.	8 (4)	6 (3)	4 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.00	Accepted
10	I find it very easy to teach Agricultural science with improvised instructional materials.	7 (4)	6 (3)	4 (2)	3 (1)	20	2.85	Accepted
11	I always feel happy to improvise instructional materials.	13 (4)	6 (3)	1 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.60	Accepted
12	I find the improvisation of instructional materials a comfortable exercise.	9 (4)	7 (3)	2 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.15	Accepted
13	I am enthusiastic about improvisation of instructional materials.	4 (4)	0 (3)	9 (2)	7 (1)	20	2.05	Rejected
14	I always find it interesting to improvise instructional materials.	3 (4)	2 (3)	12 (2)	8 (1)	20	2.40	Rejected
15	Improvised instructional materials are not too local for teaching Agricultural science.	3 (4)	2 (3)	9 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.10	Rejected

Keys: SA= Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, NR = Number of Respondents

In the table 4 above, item 8 shows the mean of 3.70 that implies that improvisation of instructional materials improve teaching and learning Agricultural science. Item 9 shows the mean of 3.00 it also means knowledge of improvisation enables teacher to be self fulfilled. Item 10 has a mean of 2.85 it shows that it is easy to teach Agricultural science with improvised instructional materials. Item 11 shows the mean of 3.60 so they are always feel happy to improvised instructional materials. Item 12 has the mean point of 3.15 it is also shows that improvisation of instructional materials is cumbersome. Item 13

shows the mean values of 2.05 which indicated that respondents were not enthusiastic about improvisation of instructional materials. Item 14 shows the mean value of 2.40 implies that respondents always find it not interesting to improvise instructional materials. Lastly item 15 table 4 shows also shows the mean value of 2.10 which indicated that respondents rejected the statement that said improvised instructional materials are not too local.

In the table 5 below item 16 shows the mean of 3.05 this implies that improvisation helps in developing problem solving skills in teaching Agricultural science. Item 17 has a mean value of 3.70 which shows that improvisation helps teachers to teach skills in Agricultural science lesson. Item 18 with a mean point of 3.50 it means improvisation helps to stimulate student's interest in Agricultural science lesson. Item 19 has a mean point of 3.05 improvisation of instructional materials make teachers more resourceful. Item 20 has a mean of 3.80 so it is also shown that improvisation helps students to develop creative skills. Item 21 was rejected by the respondents with the mean value of 2.00 as shown. While item number 22 with a mean of 3.40 shows that improvisation promote development in local craft men. Item 23 has a mean of 3.05 it is also shows that improvisation aids students in acquisition of scientific skills. Lastly item 24 has a mean point of 3.50 it is also means improvisation materials cover the three domains of educational objectives

Research Question Three: *What are the roles of improvisation of instructional materials in effective teaching Agricultural Science in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?*

Table 5: means of the respondents on the role of improvisation toward enhancing learning

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	NR	Mean	Remarks
16	It helps in developing students problems solving skills in Agricultural science	8 (4)	7 (3)	3 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.05	Accepted
17	It helps teachers manipulative skills in Agricultural science lesson	15 (4)	4 (3)	1 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.70	Accepted
18	It helps to stimulate students interest Agricultural science lesson	12 (4)	6 (3)	2 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.50	Accepted
19	Improvisation of materials make teachers more resourceful.	9 (4)	5 (3)	4 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.05	Accepted
20	It helps the students to develop creative skills.	16 (4)	4 (3)	0 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.80	Accepted
21	It helps the teachers to develop technical skills.	2 (4)	2 (3)	10 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.00	Rejected
22	It promote technological development in local craft men	12 (4)	4 (3)	4 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.40	Accepted
23	It contribute student's acquisition of scientific skills.	8 (4)	6 (3)	5 (2)	1 (1)	20	3.05	Accepted
24	Effective improvisation covers the three domains of educational objectives.	13 (4)	5 (3)	1 (2)	1 (1)	20	3.50	Accepted

Keys: SA=Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, NR = Number of Respondents.

In the table 6 below item 25 shows the mean value of 3.15 this implies Improvisation is beneficial to the academic achievement of students. Item 26 shows lower mean value of 2.00 respondents rejected that Knowledge of improvisation enables me to be self-fulfilled as a teacher. Item 27 shows the mean value of 3.50 implies that respondents find it very easy to teach Agricultural science with improvised instructional materials. Item 28 shows the mean value of 3.05 which indicated that respondents always feel happy to improvise instructional materials. Item 29 shows the mean value of 3.00 which indicated that respondents find improvisation of instructional materials a comfortable exercise. Item 30 shows the mean value of 2.85 which means respondents were so enthusiastic about improvisation of instructional materials. Item 31 shows the mean value of 3.60 that means they are always interesting to improvise instructional materials. And lastly item 32 shows the mean value of 2.00 which implies that respondents were not happy with the statement that improvised instructional materials are not too local for teaching instructional materials Agricultural science.

Research Question four: *What are the challenges faced by Agricultural Science teachers in improvisation of instructional materials in secondary in Yobe south senatorial zone?*

Table 6. Means of the respondents on the challenges faced Agricultural Science teachers in improvisation of instructional materials toward enhancing learning.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	NR	X	Remarks
25	Improvisation is beneficial to the academic achievement of students.	9 (4)	7 (3)	2 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.15	Accepted
26	Knowledge of improvisation enables me to be self-fulfilled as a teacher.	2 (4)	2 (3)	10 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.00	Rejected
27	I find it very easy to teach Agricultural science with improvised instructional materials.	12 (4)	6 (3)	2 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.50	Accepted
28	I always feel happy to improvise instructional materials.	9 (4)	5 (3)	4 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.05	Accepted
29	I find the improvisation of instructional materials a comfortable exercise.	8 (4)	6 (3)	4 (2)	2 (1)	20	3.00	Accepted
30	I am enthusiastic about improvisation of instructional materials.	7 (4)	6 (3)	4 (2)	3 (1)	20	2.85	Accepted
31	I always find it interested to improvise instructional materials	13 (4)	6 (3)	1 (2)	0 (1)	20	3.60	Accepted
32	Improved instructional materials are not too local for teaching instructional materials Agricultural science.	2 (4)	2 (3)	10 (2)	6 (1)	20	2.00	Rejected

Keys: SA=Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed, NR = Number of Respondents

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings of the research question regarding the improvisation of instructional materials for teaching and learning Agricultural science in senior secondary school in Yobe south senatorial zone. The result on the tables indicates that there is no provision of facilities for effective teaching of Agricultural science Ololube, (2016) who observed that poor availability and ineffective use of instructional materials

result in low student performance. These may be due to lack of knowledge and experience on how to utilize some of these instructional materials during teaching this is in line with the findings of Ugwu (2015). Stressing on the problems of effective utilization of instructional materials. He reported that untrained teachers are employed to teach in our secondary schools and colleges due to insufficient training, many teachers do not recognize the potential of many simple teaching aids available at very little cost on how to use them. The implication of this is that the students will not be able to acquire the necessary skills and attitude expected of them at this level of educational.

This may result in student's choice of Agricultural science as a course at higher levels. In these results, the Agricultural science teachers have shown that there is gross inadequacy of instructional materials for teaching in the schools. The findings are also in line with Anyakoha (2004), who noted that all over Nigeria, materials for teaching are less available Olaitin (1990) lamented that without the provision of adequate teaching materials in schools for teaching. It also resonates with Anyanwu, (2019), who observed that modern agricultural science requires innovative teaching approaches beyond traditional tools. The achievement of the Agricultural science curriculum objectives might be quite impossible. Also the unavailability of laboratory equipment's, chemicals goes with the findings of Kamar, (2007) which revealed that lack of laboratory equipment's, chemicals and laboratory assistance are reported by teachers as the major constraints militating against the conduct of practical work in schools.

Overall, the findings confirm the consensus in literature that improvisation is a vital strategy for effective teaching of agricultural science in under-resourced environments. The study revealed that teachers in Yobe south senatorial zone are willing and competent but constrained by systemic challenges such as insufficient government provision, lack of laboratories, and inadequate professional development. This reinforces Abeelnsa & Moola (2017), who reported that improvisation improves learner performance in under-resourced classrooms

Summary of the study

The primary issue on which the study focused was to find the improvisation and utilization of instructional materials for teaching Agricultural science in senior secondary school within the zone. The study reveals that;

1. There are inadequate instructional materials for teaching and learning Agricultural science in senatorial zone and the few available.
2. One is not utilized by the Agricultural science teachers. This it may be attributed to lack of knowledge and experience of some teachers on how to utilize the instructional materials during teaching/learning process.
3. Lack of funds for the production (improvisation) of instructional materials for teaching and learning in secondary schools.

CONCLUSION

Literature has indicated that instructional materials can improve learning outcomes among students (Anyakoha, 2004; Olaitan 2008). An instructional materials on its own may have little value for learning unless teachers use it in classrooms. The findings of this study shows that the Agricultural science teachers have negative attitude toward improvisation of instructional materials. The inability of the majority of the teachers to improvise instructional materials implies that the benefit of improvisation to Agricultural science education is not been achieved. The findings of this study indicated that materials for teaching Agricultural science were largely available, there was low extent of teacher's utilization of available instructional materials by the teachers and Agricultural science teachers improvised few of the instructional materials available for teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the above findings, the following recommendations are made;

1. The ministry of education officials should make sure that laboratory equipment is supplied to schools and the quantity should be supplied according to the number of students available in each school.
2. Ministry of education should make appropriate plan to expose Agricultural science teachers to training workshops or improvisation in order to update their techniques and also attend conference, seminars and workshops on materials resources productions, utilization and management.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to commit themselves into effective use of instructional materials in all their instructional delivery.
4. Government at various levels should adequately fund science education so as to encourage teachers to improvise instructional materials.

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